

LIVE WEIGHT INDICATORS OF ZAAZEN GOATS FROM FOREIGN BREEDS RAISED IN THE CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT AGE AND CONSTITUTION TYPE

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Abstract. In this article, the growth indicators of goats of the Zaanen breed brought from abroad, bred in the conditions of Karakalpakstan, according to different age and constitution type, were studied for the first time. The obtained data were compared with the standard indicators.

Key words. Zaanen goat breed, live weight, growth factor.

Actuality of the topic. Based on the study of the laws of growth and development of agricultural animals, it is possible to create appropriate types of animals. Knowing these laws, it is possible to systematically control these processes by influencing the growth and development of animals with the help of various external and internal factors. General laws of personal development include continuous, uneven, periodic, correlative, adaptive development. From the formation of the zygote to old age and natural death, the body undergoes continuous quantitative and qualitative changes [4].

Growth is quantitative changes in the organism, in which the overall dimensions of the animal, live weight and the shape of individual organs change and increase. An important indicator of growth is the live weight of animals. Live weight at birth is also an important selection indicator. Due to the fact that the animal organism is in regular contact with the external environment surrounding it, the growth and development processes of different animals are different [3].

Live weight of farm animals is also determined by weighing in the zootechnical practice. It should be emphasized that growth always occurs with the development of the organism. Development is understood as the process of morphological and physiological changes that occur during individual development (ontogenesis) of an animal organism. In a word, tissues and organs are qualitatively renewed and specialized. Live weight in all farm animals is an important biological and economic indicator. The mark of live weight depends on the type, breed, sex, age, feeding and storage conditions, and specific individual characteristics of the animal.

Animals with relatively large bodies tend to store nutrients in their bodies. With an increase in live weight, relatively more reserves are collected in the animal's body, and this reserve is used for the body's metabolism when there is a shortage of nutrients. Larger animals within this breed and herd are usually distinguished by a healthy, rather robust constitution [6].

The Zaanen goat breed is considered to be the world's smoothest breed. The birthplace of the Zaanen goat breed is the area around the Zaane River in the Bern Alps (Switzerland). This breed was created in the 19th century [7].

The Zaanen breed is one of the largest in the world. The live weight of an adult breed goat is 70-80 kg, and some of them reach 100 kg. In adult female goats, the live weight index reaches 50-60 kg, in some even up to 90 kg [3; 5].

The source and method of the research. Research on the dependence of live weight on age and constitution type in Zaanen goats was conducted at the farm "PANAEV FARMS" located in the Karaozak district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. 300 female goats and 10 male goats aged 7-8 months were brought to this farm from Austria in May 2017. Female goats were selected as the research object. These goats were divided into dense, thin and robust constitution type groups based on the generally accepted method of determining constitution type in zootechnics. Each group consisted of ten goats ($n=10$), which were maintained under the same feed and condition. Growth and live weight of goats at 8 months, 12 months, 18 months and 24 months of age were measured before feeding in the morning on electronic platform scale brand "Super AOTE". The technical capability of the scale is from min-400 g to max-200 kg, and the accuracy level is ± 20 g. Growth factors were calculated by dividing the live weight at the end of the period by the live weight at the beginning of the period. The received digital data were biometrically processed using the Microsoft Office Excel 2007 computer program [1], and the average arithmetic value and its error ($\bar{X} \pm S_x$), coefficient of variation ($C_v\%$) were calculated. Differences between groups were compared using confidence criteria ($R < 0.05$; $R < 0.01$);).

The obtained results and their analysis. In our country, in particular, in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in order to develop goat breeding and increase milk production, goats of Zaanen breed are imported from abroad. However, there are almost no studies on the growth, development and productivity of imported dairy Zaanen goats in the new Karakalpakstan ecological conditions. Therefore, determining how constitution type and related live weight changes at different ages in imported zaanen goats allows to make a preliminary conclusion about how goats grow and adapt to a new environmental environment.

In the course of research, live weight indicators of Zaanen goats of different constitutions and ages were studied. It should be noted that goats of strong constitution type differed from other goats of the same age in terms of body structure and live weight. This can also be seen from the data presented in the table.

table

Live weight dynamics of goats, kg (n-10)

Age, month	Constituion type					
	Strong		Dense		Thin	
	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	$C_v \%$	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	$C_v \%$	$\bar{X} \pm S_x$	$C_v \%$
8	27,4±0,44**	5,04	26,3±0,44	5,29	25,5±0,43	5,38
12	35,1±0,54**	4,87	33,6±0,52	4,93	32,4±0,53	5,12
18	40,4±0,54**	4,68	39,3±0,51*	4,13	37,6±0,57	4,83
24	45,6±0,61**	4,21	44,0±0,79	5,64	42,5±0,73	5,41

Note: * P<0,05; ** P<0,01;

It can be seen from the table that the goats of strong constitution type outperformed goats of the same age in terms of live weight. In particular, at the age of eight months, it was 1.1 kg (R>0.05) or 4.19% more than dense constitution type goats, and 1.9 kg (R<0.01) or 7.45% more than thin constitution type goats. The results of the analysis of goats in the period of one year of age show that the average live weight of goats of strong constitution type was 35.1±0.54 kg. According to this indicator, live weight was heavier by 1.5 kg (R>0.05) or 4.46% and by 2.7 kg (R<0.01) or 8.33%, respectively.

Physiological conditioning of goats is important in obtaining offspring. Therefore, the live weight during the foaling period is also important for the normal metabolism of the mother and the embryo. The live weight of goats at the age of one and a half years, i.e. 18 months, is 40.4±0.54 kg in goats with strong constitution type, 39.3±0.51 kg in goats with dense constitution type, and 37 kg in goats with thin constitution type. It was 6±0.57 kg. In this case, goats of strong and dense constitution type have an advantage of 2.8 kg (R<0.01) or 7.45% and 1.7 kg (R<0.05) or 4.52%, respectively, than other goats of the same age of thin constitution type.

The same trend was observed in goats aged twenty-four months. In particular, the highest live weight indicator was observed in the strong type with an average of 45.6±0.61 kg, and the lowest live weight indicator was observed in the thin type with an average of 42.5±0.73 kg. The dense constitution type

recorded an intermediate live weight index with an average of 44.0 ± 0.79 kg. The difference between goats of strong and thin constitution type is 3.1 kg ($R < 0.01$), or 7.29%, and the difference between goats of dense and thin constitution type is 1.5 kg ($R > 0.05$), or 3.53%.

In order to more fully study the dynamics of live weight, the coefficients of growth of live weight by age periods of goats were also calculated. The resulting digital data is presented in the form of a diagram in the figure.

Figure. Live weight growth coefficients of goats of different ages and constitution types

It can be seen from the live weight growth ratio of the goats in the chart that between 8-12 months of age, the strong and dense constitution type goats in the experiment had a ratio of 1.28 and gained live weight at the same rate. In goats of delicate constitution type, this coefficient corresponded to 1.27. This means that in this age range, the thin type gained live weight at a slightly lower rate. A change in the ratio of growth coefficients of live weight of goats in the age range of 12-18 months was observed, and it can be seen that goats of dense constitution type dominated the growth coefficient of goats of dense constitution type with a coefficient of 1.17, goats of strong constitution type 1.16 and goats of thin constitution type 1.15. But in the age range of 18-24 months of goats, dense type showed a decrease in growth coefficient compared to strong and thin type. In this age range, the growth rate of the strong and thin type was the same, and recorded a coefficient of 1.13. In dense type goats, this coefficient corresponded to 1.12. From the indicators of the growth coefficient, it can be seen that the dense constitution type grows relatively faster in the age range of

8-12 and 12-18 months. Although the thin constitution type had a lower index compared to the strong type in terms of live weight dynamics, it corresponded to almost similar indicators in terms of growth coefficient.

Conclusion. From the analysis of the obtained results, it can be concluded that the dynamics of weight depends on the type of constitution, and this indicator is relatively high in strong type goats. Specifically, at the age of eight months, 1.1 kg ($R>0.05$) or 4.19% of dense constitution type goats, and 1.9 kg ($R<0.01$) or 7.45% of thin constitution type goats; by 1.5 kg ($R>0.05$) or 4.46% and 2.7 kg ($R<0.01$) or 8.33% respectively at the age of twelve months; 2.8 kg ($R<0.01$) or 7.45% and 1.7 kg ($R<0.05$) or 4.52%, respectively, of goats of strong and dense constitution type at the age of eighteen months compared to thin constitution type of other goats at the same age to; At twenty-four months of age, the difference between goats of strong and thin constitution type was 3.1 kg ($R<0.01$), or 7.29%, and the difference between goats of dense and thin constitution type was 1.5 kg ($R>0, 05$) or 3.53%. But the growth rate shows that each type grows at almost the same rate for the corresponding age periods.

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